

THE REACTION OF BROMINE WITH THIOCARBAMIDE.
CONSTITUTION OF FORMAMIDINE DISULPHIDE

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Bromine reacts in an indifferent solvent medium with thiocarbamide or its oxidation product, the 'formamidine disulphide' (hydrobromide) forming the same bromine addition product which is not a 'perbromide' but has both its bromines held probably with singlet links. From the properties of this compound it is suggested that the so-called 'formamidine disulphide' is not a true 'disulphide' but is derived from a single thiocarbamide molecule. The structural possibilities of such a compound are pointed out.

The reaction of bromine with thiocarbamide has been studied by Claus (*Annalen*, 1875, 179, 135), McGowan (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1887, 51, 378), and Hunter and Jones (*ibid.*, 1930, 2197, 2211). Claus used an alcoholic medium and obtained a colorless product which he called dithiocarbamide dibromide (I). Identity of his product with Storch's base (*Monatsh*, 1890, 11, 452), the so-called formamidine disulphide (II; Werner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 2166, 2180; Fichter and Wenk, *Ber.*, 1912, 45 1374), came to be recognised later.

Hunter and Jones (*loc. cit.*), who used a carbon disulphide medium for the reaction, reported formation of an unstable, ill defined, red 'perbromide' (III), which decomposed into HBr and a product "CSN₂H₃Br" identical with Claus' compound :

These authors do not appear to have investigated in any detail the nature of their 'perbromide' nor did they suggest any explanation for the apparent difference in the composition of their compound (IV) with that of (I).

The present investigation has shown that in an inert solvent medium the thiocarbamide or its oxidation product, the "formamidine disulphide" hydrobromide, interacts with bromine forming the same product, a well defined bromine-addition compound, the 'perbromide' of Hunter and Jones (*loc. cit.*).

The 'red' colour of the compound and its unstable nature led Hunter and Jones to suggest by analogy, with the well known derivatives, which Hunter *et al.* obtained from aromatic thiocarbamides, a perbromide constitution for it. The compound, however, shows considerable departures from a typical perbromide *e. g.*,

(i) It is too unstable as compared to perbromides generally, and particularly those from aromatic thiocarbamides.

(ii) It is extraordinarily sensitive to moisture and almost instantaneously reacts with water discharging its colour.

(iii) It cannot be used as a brominating agent, but the labile bromine atoms always react with the thiocarbamide residue itself.

(iv) It is not soluble to any considerable extent in organic solvents or water. If it had a hydroperbromide structure, in view of its saline character and the easy solubility of thiocarbamide and formamidine disulphide salts, it would have been sensibly soluble in these solvents, and above all,

(v) Under certain well defined conditions it liberates two equivalents of iodine from aqueous potassium iodide suggesting thereby that both the bromines are labile.

In view of these facts and the considerations that (1) aromatic thiocarbamides react with bromine in an inert solvent medium forming arylaminothiazoles, which are derived from *single molecules* of thiocarbamides, (2) no disulphide formation is known from aromatic thiocarbamides (this *Journal*, 1945, 22, 37) and (3) Dixon has shown (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 2515, *et seq.*) that when alkyl and acyl halides react with thiocarbamide, the initial reaction in all cases takes place at the sulphur atom but, subsequently the halogen is dislodged as an anion and in many cases the alkyl or acyl residue migrates on to nitrogen, especially, when it is a negative group like CH_3CO , etc., the following mechanism of bromine addition is suggested as the most probable :

The hydrobromide (V) has apparently one of its bromines as an anion, while the other is held co-valently by nitrogen. Since, however, both these atoms by themselves are identical in every respect, there is little reason to suppose that their links with thiocarbamide molecule can be so sharply differentiated. In other words, there would be resonance between the above two types of bonds and the actual state may be represented as (VIa) or (VIb)

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Action of Bromine with Thiocarbamide in CHCl₃, CCl₄ or CS₂.—Finely powdered thiocarbamide (3.8 g.) was suspended in the dry solvent (50 c.c.) and bromine (8.5 g., little over two atomic proportions), dissolved in a few c.c. of the same solvent, was added gradually with shaking. The mixture warmed up a little and assumed an orange-red colour. It was allowed to stand overnight and the precipitate filtered; a deep red or orange product was obtained. This was dried for sometime in an oven at 45°-50° and then kept in a vacuum desiccator over solid caustic soda until free from adsorbed bromine (negative starch iodide paper test). A yellow powder which fumed copiously in moist air (recalling the behaviour of PCl₅) giving out hydrobromic acid vapours (but no free bromine) was obtained. This is the bromine-addition compound. (Found: Br, 67.50, 67.20. CSN₂H₄Br₂ requires Br, 67.79 per cent).

When carefully heated in a capillary it did not show any perceptible change up to 125°-130°, but by the time temperature had reached 140° copious evolution of HBr (but no bromine) started. The compound softened at 170°-175° and finally melted at 180° (decomp.). Even in presence of a large excess of bromine the same product was obtained. The remarkable constancy of its composition and its marked thermostability leave little doubt about its being a well defined compound and not a mixture or an adsorption compound.

The Behaviour of the Bromine-addition Compound towards Water.—The bromine-addition product is extremely sensitive to moisture. If left in an open watch-glass it continues to evolve HBr fumes until finally it has lost all its colour. In two experiments this loss has been estimated to be 32.46% and 33.1% which, considering the very unstable nature of the compound, is in fair agreement with the change:

which requires 34.3%.

When treated with a small quantity of water or rectified spirit, the yellow colour is at once discharged and a crystalline product is obtained along with the formation of hydrobromic acid. Weighed quantities of the compound thus treated were titrated with *N*/10 sodium hydroxide using phenolphthalein as an indicator:

(a) 0.3024 g. dissolved in 100 c.c. water requires 25.25 c.c. corresponding to 67.6% HBr; (b) 0.2360 g. treated as above requires 19.6 c.c. which corresponds to 67.25% HBr. This indicates that both the bromines form HBr by hydrolysis.

It was, however, noted that if very concentrated solutions of the bromine-addition compound in water were titrated with strong sodium hydroxide solution, the quantity of alkali needed fell short of the above estimate:

(a) 1.930 g. taken with 10 c.c. water requires 6.00 c.c. of 2.4 *N*-NaOH which corresponds to 60.4% HBr.

(b) 1.2844 g. treated as above requires 4.30 c.c. NaOH corresponding to 65% HBr.

(c) 1.4870 g. in 10-15 c.c. alcohol requires 4.65 c.c. alkali which amounts to 60.8% HBr.

From these results it is clear that under the conditions obtaining in these experiments all the bromine of the compound is not converted into HBr as happens in more dilute solutions. According to Werner (*loc. cit.*) $(\text{CSN}_2\text{H}_4)_2\text{I}_2$ exists in two modifications: one as hydriodide and other as co-valently held iodine compound.

Behaviour of the Bromine-addition Compound towards Aqueous Potassium Iodide.—The bromine-addition compound liberates iodine from aqueous potassium iodide solutions. To a small measured quantity of water excess of potassium iodide was added so as to leave enough salt undissolved; to this was added a known quantity of the bromine derivative, when iodine was at once liberated. It was estimated as usual with a normal solution of thiosulphate.

TABLE I

1 Expt.No	Conc. of bromine derivative				
	2 Weight.	3 Volume of water.	4 KI added.	5 Thiosulphate.	6 Thiosulphate required for 2.36g. (1/100th mole) of bromine derivative as calc. from columns 2 & 5).
1	2.0452 g.	5 c.c.	Excess till solid was left	11.57 c.c.	13.29
2	0.6294	10	Do	4.28	16.05
3	0.4662	"	Do	3.24	16.40
4	0.2634	"	Do	1.87	16.75
5	0.1016	"	Do	0.77	17.98
6	2.1876	15 (alcohol)	Do	12.00	12.95
7	2.2296	300	7-8 g.	7.78	8.33
8	1.1872	400	Do	4.41	8.76

Experiment 5, where the proportion of potassium iodide is highest with respect to the bromine-addition compound, shows maximum iodine liberation which corresponds almost to 90% of the theoretically expected (20 c.c. of *N*-thiosulphate). Smaller quantities of iodine liberated in other experiments are undoubtedly due to the utilisation of a part of the bromine for the oxidation of thiocarbamide itself (McGowan, *loc. cit.*). In experiments 7 and 8 the quantity liberated is less than even one atomic proportion. This can most probably be explained as follows.

the bromine of the "formamidine disulphide" salt formed in (i) being incapable of oxidising KI under the conditions obtaining in these experiments (cf. Werner, *loc. cit.* Werner and Reynolds, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 83, 7). This will be discussed in a separate communication.

Identity of the Hydrobromide (IV) with Formamidine Disulphide Hydrobromide.—The bromine-addition compound was treated with a small quantity of water and the

hydrobromide (IV) formed was filtered and purified by crystallisation from water or alcohol. By treating its aqueous solutions with appropriate acids nitrate, chloride and picrate were prepared : Nitrate, m.p. 82-85° or 140°(d) ; Picrate, m.p. 154° or 164° (d) ; Hydrochloride, m. p. 185-190° (d).

The exhibition of two melting points (either one or the other) by the nitrate and the picrate are undoubtedly due to their dimorphism (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1948, Part III, p. 25). The same salts were prepared from "formamidine disulphide" by Werner's procedure (*loc. cit.*). They also showed the same melting points as recorded above. Mixed melting point of the corresponding compounds showed no depression.

Preparation of the Bromine-addition Compound from 'Formamidine Disulphide' Hydrobromide.—A pure crystalline sample of the "formamidine disulphide" hydrobromide was triturated in a glass mortar with excess of bromine in chloroform. A yellow product, identical in all respects with the bromine-addition compound, directly formed from thiocarbamide and bromine, was obtained.

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